

LOCKIN-THERMOGRAPHY FOR NDE OF CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The high specific strength of CFRP laminates depends on the integrity of boundaries. Therefore methods are required that allow for the detection of delaminations, impacts, and imbedded material without affecting the performance of the inspected component. So one needs methods of nondestructive evaluation (NDE) which are sensitive to boundaries and their deterioration. In this paper we show that lockin-thermography based on modulated heat transport is well suited for monitoring the integrity of CFRP laminates remotely in a short time. Hence the method allows for in-service monitoring of safety relevant aerospace components.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers are of interest in applications where specific strength is the significant quantity of interest. Strength of light weight structures is important in all airplane and spacecraft structures where cost due to failure exceeds by orders of magnitude the price of the component that failed. Hence there is considerable interest to detect faults at an early stage either on the production line or during regular inspection intervals. As the inspection process should not affect the integrity or the performance of the inspected component, it is obvious that there is a need for reliable methods of nondestructive evaluation (NDE) allowing to detect hidden faults.

There is a broad variety of NDE methods. Many of them have been developed for the inspection of metals, they may not be suited for the inspection of CFRP and the specific faults to be detected. The performance of CFRP depends critically on the integrity of the boundaries within a laminate. So some topics of interest are delaminations, imbedded material, stringer adhesion, and quality of repair. These topics can be traced back to the problem of boundary characterisation. So from the spectrum of NDE methods mostly those are of interest which are sensitive to boundaries.

Boundaries can be probed due to their impedance mismatch which causes reflection of waves. The mismatch depends on the kind of waves that is used. Elastic waves are excellent tools to detect hidden boundaries and to locate them. However, they require usually physical contact with the object under inspection, and immersion in a water tank is a major task if a big structural component needs to be examined. Heat transport is based on high frequency phonons which are basically ultrasonics. Therefore heat propagation offers another probe for inspection.

Though heat propagation is basically a diffusion process it has been shown very early [1] that the way how modulated temperature propagates can be described by the concept of a heavily damped "thermal wave" which undergoes all kinds of interaction like any other wave. The introduction of photothermal detection [2] allows to perform thermal wave investigations in a remote way. As depth range depends on thermal diffusion length [3] one needs low frequencies to look deep into material. For 2 mm thickness CFRP the frequency is well below 1 Hz even if one uses signal phase which is known to have more depth range [4-7]. Therefore point by point raster scans across CFRP are too slow for industrial applications. So the problem was how thermal wave measurements can be performed faster at low frequencies.

MULTIPLEX THERMAL WAVES = LOCKIN-THERMOGRAPHY

The solution was to perform the point measurements not one after the other but rather in parallel: During one modulation cycle many points are observed simultaneously. Various approaches have been published how one can modify standard thermographic or video equipment to perform such multiplexed measurements. The result is that from thermographic measurements one derives finally images that display local thermal wave magnitude or phase. That is why the technique is called lockin "thermography" [8-10]. The basic pinciple that we use in our experiments is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Basic principle of lockin-thermography (I = excitation, x = pixel address, s = thermal wave signal reconstructed for x_1)

The thermal wave source (lamp or warm air) is sinusoidally modulated at a frequency corresponding to $\frac{1}{4}$ of the image frequency. So during each modulation each image pixel provides four times data which differ in phase by 90 degrees. From these four data one can reconstruct the modulation for this specific pixel (x_1 in Fig. 1) and therefrom local magnitude and phase of temperature modulation.

$$A(x_1) = \sqrt{(S_3 - S_1)^2 + (S_4 - S_2)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\varphi(x_1) = \text{arctg} \frac{S_3 - S_1}{S_4 - S_2} \quad (2)$$

In reality we take more than just four pictures $S_1 \dots S_4$ to derive therefrom the phase angle image and the magnitude image: We average over several modulation cycles, also we take more than only four images during each cycle. But due to the sinusoidal modulation all the images can finally be compressed into only four ($S_1 \dots S_4$) from which magnitude and phase are derived according to the equations above.

From these equations it is obvious that due to the ratio the phase is not affected by inhomogeneity of heat transfer, local changes of absorption coefficient, or of thermal infrared emission coefficient. So it avoids all complications usually related with the interpretation of thermographic images. Besides these advantages of phase angle images [11] one has the additional advantage that depth range is longer [4-7]. The equipment that we use consists of a conventional AGEMA 900 system combined with a synchronising equipment for coherent sinusoidal thermal wave generation and computer controlled lamps or warm air generator. In addition to these two methods we also used the loss mechanism of ultrasonic waves as a heating mechanism. In these cases the ultrasonic energy was amplitude modulated at a low frequency to act as a thermal wave generator [12]. In the following we present examples for imaging of various kinds of defects in CFRP using lockin-thermography. Each image was taken and evaluated within about 5 minutes.

DELAMINATIONS

Figure 2. CFRP sample with delamination area investigated with lockin-thermography at 0.03 Hz (left: amplitude, right: phase). The surface optical structure (white paint line IKP) is suppressed in phase image

Delaminations may have their origin in the manufacturing process or later on due to excessive load. Such an example is shown in Fig. 2 for a sample provided with optical/infrared surface structure. The magnitude image is dominated by the letters "IKP" while in the phase angle image they are almost completely suppressed (besides their effect on the signal to noise ratio) to reveal the thermal structure which displays an extended delamination on the left side.

Delaminations may also be the result of an in-service event, e.g. an impact. An example of this kind is presented in Fig. 3 where the subsurface honeycomb structure underneath the laminate is imaged together with an impact. This phase angle image was obtained with a lamp modulated at 0.06 Hz. Total phase angle range in this image is less than 3 degrees. An impact damage is characterised by additional local boundaries making modulated heat transport slower. That is why boundaries show up in phase angle images generated with modulated lamp light or warm air.

Figure 3. Detection of CFRP (1 mm thickness) and Al honeycomb structure with impact damage and delaminations

On the other hand the impact damage is an area of increased loss angle (friction) and stress concentration. Therefore in an oscillating sample the local hysteresis effect is stronger in such an area thereby revealing the impact by its excessive heat generation [13]. Fig. 4 shows the lockin-thermography image of a sample vibrating at 310 Hz for loss angle heating where an amplitude modulation of 0.04 Hz was applied to generate low frequency thermal waves. The magnitude (Fig. 4a) and phase (Fig. 4b) images were synchronised with respect to this low frequency and hence display the impact from its effect on low frequency thermal waves. The advantage of this amplitude modulation technique is that high frequency elastic waves are efficient for hysteresis heating while the low frequency modulation allows for significant depth range. This advantage is stronger at higher frequencies. Under this aspect it is rather straightforward to use ultrasonic waves for energy deposition and to monitor their local attenuation by the generated heat. This is similar to an ultrasonic C-scan with the difference that here the ultrasonic losses are imaged in a remote way at video frequency. The ultrasonic energy deposition requires physical contact between the transducer and the component under inspection. The sample used to generate Fig. 5 was coupled to an ultrasonic source on one side while the other side was monitored by the thermographic camera. Again the vibrational input was amplitude modulated at a low frequency to which lockin detection was synchronised. The sample contained three impact points which appear as bright spots. This is very much like dark field methods in microscopy where defects are visible against a darker background. In lockin-vibrothermography the background appears dark since less energy is generated outside defect areas.

Fig. 4. Magnitude (a) and phase (b) images of the backside of a CFRP sample with an impact damage. Vibration frequency: 310 Hz, modulation frequency: 0.04 Hz.

Fig. 5. Lock-in vibrothermographic magnitude (a) and phase (b) images of the backside of a CFRP plate with three impact damages.

As depth range depends on modulation frequency one has a chance of depth profiling by comparing images taken at different frequencies. The two images shown in Fig. 6 were taken at 0.03 Hz and 0.93 Hz using a lamp as a thermal wave source. As the square root of frequency is involved the depth range is by a factor of 5 larger for the 0.03 Hz image. So it shows features which are not visible in the "high frequency" image. The difference between these features would reveal the defects within a certain depth interval.

Figure 6. Phase images of CFRP sample with lockin thermography at 0.93 Hz (a) and 0.03 Hz (b) show the depth dependent delaminations

IMBEDDED MATERIAL

The contrast mechanism involved in thermal wave imaging is given by the difference of impedance and by the distance from the surface. Therefore the identification of imbedded material may be difficult. To investigate this effect we used a CFRP sample where circular Teflon sheets had been placed at various depths while in the other direction of the sample the diameter of the sheets was modified. In the lockin-thermography image obtained with a lamp at 0.03 Hz (Fig. 7) depth increases from left to right. As the distance between the Teflon inserts is constant it is obvious that one set is missing while left of it the Teflon appears white, and it appears black on the right side. So the contrast changes sign, and features disappear at a certain depth because contrast is zero. Though this looks rather confusing, it helps to determine depth since theory is well established.

Figure 7. Phase image at 0.03 Hz reveals the embedded Teflon films in CFRP laminate at different depths

INSPECTION OF REPAIR

The quality of repair is given by the quality of boundaries. Therefore it is important to see how homogeneous a repair area appears. An example is Fig. 8 where the thermal wave was in one case (Fig. 8a) generated at the rear surface of the sample by using warm air modulated at 0.03 Hz. The repair pad has a clean circular geometry, the three bright spots are due to strain gauges that were used to monitor the mechanical properties of the repair. For practical applications it is more relevant to use single ended inspection. Fig. 8b shows the same repair when the front surface is exposed to the light of a lamp modulated at 0.03 Hz. Again the circular geometry is well seen, this time together with delaminations in the outer circular part of the repair.

Figure 8. Delaminations and the repair pad of a CFRP sample can be detected from rear (a) and front (b) surface at 0.03 Hz with lamp and hot air gun respectively

CONCLUSION

We have shown that boundary defects in CFRP laminates can be imaged using multiplex thermal wave techniques ("lockin-thermography") within some minutes even at 0.03 Hz. The technique is non-destructive and also remote if one uses a modulated warm air beam or a modulated lamp for thermal wave generation. The sine wave modulation does not induce a thermal load on the sample, the temperature amplitude is usually below 5 K. So the method is really remote and nondestructive. The frequency dependent change of contrast allows for depth profiling. The technique requires only some moderate accessories in addition to existing thermographic systems.

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